

Studies in Triethylamine-Water. Part—IV : Predicting the Solubilities of Triethylamine and Water

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The solubility curve of the binary system triethylamine-water, which has a lower critical solution temperature of 18.3°, is predicted from simple thermodynamics by analysing the vapour pressure data. In this method, the equation for g^E (the molar excess free energy of mixing) of amine-water systems is assumed to hold good for temperatures at which the system is only partially miscible. The common tangential points on the curves of g^M (the molar free energy of mixing) vs X (the solvent composition, expressed in mole fraction of Et_3N in water), drawn as isotherms, reproduce the experimental solubility curve of the binary system within ± 2 per cent.

THE solubility curve of the binary system triethylamine-water has been experimentally studied by a number of workers¹⁻¹¹. The effect of ion size on the phase separation of the binary system has been brought out by comparing the effect of about 80 electrolytes on the phase separation temperature (PST) of this binary solvent mixture^{1,2}. Phase separation effects in the ternary system Et_3N -water-KI have been quantitatively predicted¹³ by using the hydration numbers of K^+ and I^- ions, obtained from conductance studies of KI in this solvent mixture¹⁴. In the present work, the solubility curve of the binary system Et_3N -water is predicted from simple thermodynamics by analysing the vapour pressure data available in literature^{4, 15-27}

Method :

The excess molar free energy of mixing, g^E , of a binary mixture can be calculated from the observed molar free energy of mixing, g^M , using the equations :

$$g^M = g^I + g^E \quad \dots (1a)$$

$$g^I = RT(1-X) \ln(1-X) + RT X \ln X \quad \dots (1b)$$

where g^I is the ideal molar free energy of mixing. g^M is calculated from vapour pressure measurements :

$$g^M = RT(1-X) \ln(p_1/p_1^0) + RT X \ln(p_2/p_2^0) \dots (2)$$

where R is the gas constant, T is the absolute temperature, p_1 and p_1^0 are the vapour pressure of water in solution and in pure form, respectively at temperature T , p_2 and p_2^0 are the vapour pressure of Et_3N in solution and in pure form, respectively at temperature T , X is the mole fraction of Et_3N in the binary mixture.

When g^M is plotted against the mole fraction of Et_3N for various temperatures, the common tangential points of the isotherm give the compositions of the coexisting phases. When the compositions of these coexisting layers are plotted against temperature, the course of the variation of these points gives the solubility curve of the binary system.

This method needs the vapour pressure data for temperatures at which the binary system is not completely miscible (in fact it is impossible to have data at these temperatures practically). Copp and Everett¹⁵ have proposed a fitting equation for g^E by modifying the one proposed by Guggenheim¹⁶. By considering only the first nine terms, the equation becomes

$$g^E/RT = AX(1-X) + X(1-X)(1-2X) \left[\frac{B+C}{(1-2X)+D(1-2X)(1-X)^6} \right] \dots (3)$$

In Et_3N -water system, equation (3) reproduces the g^E within ± 1 cal in the homogeneous regions.

The following simple assumptions are made to obtain the g^E for temperatures above the lower critical solution temperature (LCST) of Et_3N -water system :

- (i) Equation (3) holds good for temperatures at which the system is heterogeneous.
- (ii) Since the terms A , B , C and D of equation 3 all show a linear dependence on temperature below LCST in the homogeneous phase, they are considered to have the same dependency at temperatures above LCST in heterogeneous regions also.

Vapour pressure data :

Vapour pressures for Et_3N -water mixtures have been reported by various authors^{4, 15-27}. Chun and coworkers²⁰ have fitted their experimental g^E to equation 3 and have reported the values of the terms A , B , C and D for homogeneous solutions below LCST of the binary solvent mixtures.

Results and Discussion

The values of A , B , C and D against temperature have been plotted (Fig. 1) and extrapolated to temperatures upto 23°. The extrapolated values of these terms are given in Table 1. g^E is calculated

Fig. 1. Distribution ratio, D , of N-aryhydroxamic acids between CHCl_3 and aqueous HCl .

TABLE 1—VALUES OF THE TERMS A, B, C AND D OF EQUATION 3 AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES ABOVE 10°C

Temp. $^{\circ}\text{C}$	A	B	C	D
19	2.442	0.1985	0.579	1.016
20	2.456	0.2015	0.590	1.034
21	2.470	0.2045	0.602	1.050
22	2.483	0.2075	0.613	1.066
23	2.498	0.2105	0.624	1.084

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF g^M WITH SOLVENT COMPOSITION X AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

X	$-g^M$ (cal $\cdot$ mol $^{-1}$)				
	Temp. $^{\circ}\text{C}$				
	19	20	21	22	23
0.01	8.88				
0.02	11.45	8.67	8.45	8.23	8.00
0.04	18.06	11.92	10.58	10.17	9.71
0.06	13.63	12.25	11.46	10.69	9.84
0.08	14.35	12.54	11.45	10.40	9.38
0.10	15.42	13.02	11.69	10.48	9.04
0.15	19.47	13.92	12.42	10.11	9.40
0.20	24.34	14.69	15.89	14.19	12.30
0.30	38.62	22.43	20.48	18.65	16.60
0.40	41.45	31.61	29.59	27.68	25.51
0.50	47.98	39.48	37.50	35.64	38.49
0.60	52.75	46.11	44.22	42.47	40.40
0.70	55.30	51.00	49.23	47.58	45.65
0.80	55.38	53.70	52.08	50.59	48.83
0.90	50.07	54.06	52.70	51.46	50.02
		49.27	48.43	47.65	46.78

using equation 3 and g^M is calculated with equation 1. Table 2 gives the values of g^M for different temperatures. g^M vs X isotherms are drawn and the common tangential points are obtained from these isotherms (Fig. 2). Fig. 3 shows the course of the variation of the common tangential points obtained at various temperatures (Table 3).

The variation of the common tangential points of g^M -X isotherms reproduces the solubility curve of Et_3N -water system given by Kohler and Rice⁹,

Fig. 2. Estimation of K_D (CHCl_3 and aqueous phase).

Fig. 3. Estimation of K_D , chloroform and aqueous phase.

who had taken special care in the purification of the solvents. Copp and Everett¹⁵ have used this procedure to work out the solubility curve of the system methyldiethylamine-water. But in their work they assumed that the terms B, C and D are temperature independent. The curve obtained in

TABLE 8—PREDICTED VALUES OF THE COMPOSITIONS OF THE COEXISTING PHASES 1 AND 2 AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES
X = Mole fraction of Et₃N

Temp. °C	X ₁	X ₂
19	0.080	0.200
20	0.028	0.275
21	0.025	0.375
22	0.025	0.475
23	0.020	0.535

their analysis showed a second minimum, which is absent in the experimental curve. In the present work, there is no such anomaly for Et₃N-water system. The solubility curve is reproduced within ±2% of the experimental values.

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